

EUROFLEETS+Blue Skills Lab

“AUV workshop”

at UGOT - University of Gothenburg

Fiskebäckskil, November 2022

Scientific Participants

Anna Wåhlin (UGOT, Instructor)

Filip Stedt (UGOT, Instructor)

Niklas Andersson (UGOT, Administrator)

Participant list

Last name	First name	Nationality	Institute
Serimozu	Cem	Belgian	IMS METU, Turkey
Cavalinhos	Rita	Portuguese	UALG, Portugal
Varzi	Andrea Giulia	Italian	UNIMIB, Italy
Garzia	Angela	Italian	UPdM, Italy
de Oliveira	Larissa	Brazilian	UCC, Ireland
Ambias	David	Spanish	UB, Spain
Ribeiro	Clara	Portugal	UALG, Portugal
Yuan	Xiaohan	Chinese	UGOT, Sweden
SALM	KAI	ESTONIAN	TalTech, Estonia
Porrino	Roberta Saul	Italian	Uniparthenope, Italy
Enzmann-Horvath	Richard	Hungarian / British	Robotics planet, at own expense

Course objectives

An AUV workshops / training on AUV operation, organized within the Eurofleets+ training program, was held at the Robotics Lab workshop of Gothenburg University (UGOT) at the field station Kristineberg. The workshop had a duration of 5 days and was offered to European PhD and post-graduate students (students of all nationalities enrolled at European universities). Course elements included technical preparation of Autonomous Underwater Vehicles, mission planning preparation, integration of scientific payload, data acquisition and post-processing of various types of sensors with emphasize on hydroacoustic sensors (multibeam, sediment profiling, ADCP). Theoretical course elements were applied practically on board the RV Skagerak.

The participants in this workshop learnt:

- Learning (-by-doing) the logistical challenges and advantages with AUVs as research tools
- Acoustic methods for biotope classification and GIS charting
- Limitations and opportunities of AUVs as platforms
- Importance of the AUV sensor suite

11 applications were received of which 10 were accepted and one was put on a reserve list. One of the accepted applicants cancelled and the one from the reserve list was accepted and participated in the course. The 10 students are residents in 7 different European countries and are 7 different nationalities. Of the 10 students 8 were female and 2 male.

Oct 30th – Arrival at Kristineberg station

Oct 31st – The participants met in the computer lab room at Kristineberg field station. They were given a short background on the Eurofleets project and the infrastructure to be used. They were divided into four groups, and everyone made sure the software (HuginOS) and necessary maps were installed on their laptops. The goal of the first day was to get acquainted with the mission planning software and agree on a small number of missions that the group wanted to perform. At the end of the day everyone assembled, and the missions were brought up on the big screen and quality-controlled with respect to risk factors, payload requirements etc. The evening assignment was that the groups merge their missions into four joint missions that would be performed over the coming days. Skills learned included set-up software, installing maps, plan draft mission, pre-mission procedures and QC of mission plan.

Nov 1st – First field day. Participants met in the morning on RV Skagerak with the AUV on board. On-board lectures were given during transit times. First mission was done successfully. Participants participated in launch, guard keeping over emergency messages, and recovery. Simultaneous use of RV Skagerak's multibeam was done by some of the students.

Nov 2nd – Second field day

AUV launched in the morning from RV Skagerak. Workshop 'huddles' and completes post processing guide. Participants participated in launch, guard keeping over emergency messages, and recovery. Simultaneous use of RV Skagerak's multibeam was done by some of the students.

Eurofleets+ Blue Skill Labs

Nov 3rd - Third field day - AUV launched for its mission. Workshop participants working on data post processing from previous mission and report writing. After recovery, data from third mission was downloaded and quality controlled and plans for fourth mission was finalized. Participants participated in launch, guard keeping over emergency messages, and recovery. Simultaneous use of RV Skagerak's multibeam was done by some of the students.

Nov 4th – data post-processing and course report preparation. Participants working on report: describing a question, method, limitation or advantage of using AUV, optimal frequency for your application, or similar. Wrapping up on post processing document.

Infrastructure used/shown during the workshop:

The AUV at The University of Gothenburg – called Ran – has good navigation accuracy and carries high resolution acoustic sonars and other mapping instruments. There are only a few AUV:s in the world with Ran's capacity, accessible to science. Thanks to the navigational properties, it can accomplish under-ice missions, and it has been used successfully in Antarctica and under ice in Baltic sea coastal waters.

Ran is a part of the national research infrastructure MUST (Mobile Underwater System Tools), financed by the Knut and Alice Wallenberg Foundation. The infrastructure is open for external users for research purposes. Ran can also, under certain circumstances, be rented by commercial companies.

Eurofleets⁺ Blue Skill Labs

Basic data:

Model: Hugin (Kongsberg)

Length: 6.5 metres

Weight: 1850 kg (dry)

Speed: 1-7 knots, cruise speed 4 knots

Maximum dive depth: 3000 metres

Maximum dive length and time: 300 km and 36 h

Sensor suite:

multibeam echo sounder, Multibeam Kongsberg EM2040, 200-400 kHz, 0.7° x 0.7° beam width, swath coverage sector up to 140°

conductivity, temperature and depth sensor (CTD), dual systems SeaBird 911 19plusv2

oxygen sensor, SeaBird SBE43 (dual system)

carbon dioxide sensor, Contros HydroC

nitrate sensor, SeaBird Deep SUNA

chlorophyll/turbidity sensor, SeaBird WetLabs ECOtriplet (FLBBCD)

side scan sonar (= acoustic "camera"), EdgeTech 2205. Frequencies 75/410 kHz (1-6 km range)

bottom-penetrating sonar (= acoustic "X-ray camera"), EdgeTech DW216 with configurable chirp

navigation system: DVL-supported Honeywell Hg9900, gives accuracy of better than 0.08% of distance travelled

acoustic communication below surface, 2-3 km between ship and AUV satellite, radio and WiFi communication in surface mode

RV Skagerak

On board RV Skagerak the students did CTD measurements to compare and quality control AUV data. They used the ship's Kongsberg multibeam to compare with the AUVs multibeam.

Preliminary results

No results can be presented due to the nature of the course.

Evaluation of student learning

No tests were conducted as the course. The students' final group reports were all up to standard.

Students course evaluation

Like the last course from 2019, we received mainly positive feedback.

Feedback question	Number of votes	
	Yes	No
Did you find the organisers helpful during preparations?	7	0
Do you feel the course was well organized?	5	2
Was the course content interesting?	7	0
Did you get better knowledge on what scientific platform that fits best for different research questions?	7	0

Comments:

“I only suggest that you develop a guide on all mission preparation and even processing software in order to be easier to understand“

“Knowing how to solve problems and communicate with the vessel crew during the AUV mission felt very important. However, all the communication between the lead scientist and crew members to solve issues and plan missions was done in Swedish. We understand it is a Swedish vessel therefore Swedish will be spoken. But we felt a bit left out in most of the situations, especially the situations dealing with technical issues, because we could not understand the language. We would have appreciated it if the communication between Prof Anna, the captain, or Philip for example, were done in English so we could get more involved in the mission and therefore get a further understanding of the AUV deployment.“

„I would have liked to have a little more time to post process the data. Maybe two days instead of one.“

Concluding remarks

Overall, the students would have liked to have a little more time for their tasks. It was also obvious that the less experienced students did not get as much out of the course as the more experienced ones. The time on board when the AUV was doing the other group’s project was spend curiously exploring the possibilities on the research vessel by the more experienced students while the less experienced were not able to take own initiatives to the same extent. If the course is to be run again, we should consider not enrolling less experienced students or prepare more hands on tasks for them.

The course was an incredible opportunity for UGOT to showcase the possibilities on board our RV Skagerak and with the AUV to a broader group of students.